

Experimental and Numerical Study of Tubular Material by Lateral Indentation Test

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Abstract – The paper presents a new experimental apparatus is designed and manufactured to perform lateral indentation of tubular materials by hemispherical nosed punch. This study presents the development of inverse analysis methodology and its application to determine flow stress curves of metallic tubes. The inverse problem is defined as the minimization of the differences between the experimental measurements of the punch force vs. Punch stroke and the corresponding FEM predictions. Elastoplastic model based on the Hill48 yield criterion and isotropic strain gardening law is used to analyse the metal flow while a Levenberg Marquart optimization algorithm adjusts iteratively the material parameters used in the simulation until the computed outputs matches the measured data with a specific tolerance. As results of this study, it was shown that the present inverse analysis methodology could identify accurately the material parameters and offer a systematic and cost effective way for determining tube characteristics for simulation of tubular material forming processes.

Keywords: Tubular materials/ Lateral Indentation test/ Inverse analysis/ Anisotropy / FEM.

1 Introduction

The accuracy of process simulation in metal forming by FEM depends on the accuracy of flow stress data that are input to FEM codes. Therefore, it is essential that these input data values are determined using reliable tests. Tubular materials are commonly employed in automotive industries. For instance, they are used bumper bars and door intrusion to increase the absorption of impact energy [1,2]. Moreover, tube hydroforming and rotary draw bending are among the main forming processes consuming tubular structures for developing lightweight components in automotive industries.

In the last few decades, several investigations have been carried out to study the response of metallic tubes [3].

This study presents a new designed experimental apparatus to carry out tubular material characterization by lateral indentation test and using a hemispherical nosed indenter shape. The tubular experimental curve is used with a developed inverse analysis methodology and applied to determine flow stress parameters. This technique can offer a systematic and cost effective way for identifying material property data for simulation of tubular metal forming processes.

2 Experimental setup

Tubes under study were made from low carbon steel S235 with a nominal outer diameter of 50 mm and initial thickness of 1.07 mm. The steel tubes are manufactured by sheet slip rolling process then welded by High Frequency Induction Welding Process. Tensile test specimens were cut from the tube along its axial direction to measure the conventional mechanical properties and the Lankford coefficients. Figure 1 shows the experimental tooling for lateral indentation test which is mounted on a universal Shimadzu tensile testing machine.

Figure 1. Experimental tooling mounted on universal tensile machine for lateral indentation test

The two ends of the tube are retained from moving or sliding and gripped by a pair of jaw chucks that apply distributed effort around tube extremities by means of highly elastic rings. The lateral load is applied at mid-span of the tube using a rigid hemispherical nosed punch whilst the tube is laying on a flat rigid plate. The load is applied using the crosshead of the universal tensile machine running at a velocity of 5mm/min to a maximum punch stroke of 30 mm. The indenter load-displacement curve was measured to be used for the identification of the flow stress parameters. Table 1 lists the mechanical properties of tube obtained from tensile test.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the tube

$\sigma_{0.2\%}$ (MPa)	σ_{UTS} (MPa)	A%	R
367±5	408±5	36±1	1.50±0.02

3 Inverse analysis

The inverse identification approach was developed to accomplish flow stress data determination. The hybrid experimental-numerical method is based on minimization of an objective function (Eq.1) which defines a least square approximation between experimental and FEM prediction curves of the punch force vs. punch stroke

$$f(P) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{h_i^{\text{exp}} - h_i^{\text{num}}(P)}{h_i^{\text{exp}}} \right)^2} \leq \delta \quad (1)$$

Elastoplastic FEM model based on Hill48 yield criterion and isotropic strain hardening law of Swift is used to analyze the metal flow while a Levenberg Marquart optimization algorithm adjusts iteratively the material flow stress parameters used in the simulation until the computed outputs matches the measured data within a specific tolerance.

$$\bar{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{1+R} (R(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22})^2 + 2(1+R)\sigma_{12}^2) \quad (2)$$

$$Y = K(\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_{eq})^n \quad (3)$$

3D FEM model is built using ABAQUS/Standard software. It is composed of three parts: (i) the tube, a deformable media which is modelled by a fourth part owing to load and geometry symmetries. The hemispherical nosed punch is considered as a rigid body; (iii) the tube rests on a flat rigid support during the lateral indentation test. The boundary conditions are applied on the FEM model such as the first tube extremity is imbedded and for the other end located at 62.5 mm from the fixed side,

the boundary conditions are dictated by the appropriate symmetries conditions. The structure was meshed using an eight-node brick element C3D8R. This element is a general purpose linear solid element and reduced integration with hourglass control solid element. In the simulation, five integration points and three layers are considered through the tube thickness. Earlier sensitivity study was performed to optimize the FEM model to guarantee numerical accuracy results. Figure 2 shows the FEM model used in the inverse analysis to simulate the lateral tube indentation. Regarding contact between the punch, the tube and the flat support, the Coulomb's friction law is considered in all contact area. A friction coefficient of 0.08 is used.

Figure 2. Finite element model

4 Results and discussion

Running the inverse identification algorithm, the tubular material parameters are obtained after ten iterations. Figure 3 shows the iteration process during the convergence of the parameters towards the optimal values. Table 2 lists the flow stress data obtained by the inverse analysis. Figure 4 shows the experimental plots of the punch force vs. the punch displacement evolution for the low carbon steel S235. It is shown a good accuracy of the inverse identification method, and the suited strain hardening laws which fit correctly the experimental points in these plots. Moreover, one can see that the punch force increases slightly at the first stage of force increments up to a giving effort level and then the force increases significantly following a straight line up to the final displacement.

Figure 3. Parameter evolution during iteration process

Table 2. Identified flow stress parameters

Flow stress parameters	Initial parameters	Identified parameters
K	450	458,93
n	0,25	0.2075
ϵ_0	0,01	0,0196

Figure 4. Comparison between simulated and experimental force-displacement curves.

5 Conclusion

The paper presents an experimental and numerical study of a novel lateral indentation test for mechanical characterisation of tubular materials. An inverse analysis methodology is developed and applied to determine flow stress parameters of a mild steel tube S235. As results of this study, it was shown that the developed inverse method could identify accurately material parameters from one test. Therefore, this technique can offer a systematic and cost effective way for determining material properties for simulation of tube forming processes.

6 References

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